

Comparative Relationships between Self-Efficacy and Test Anxiety on Performance in Biology among Secondary School Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Comparative relationships between self-efficacy and Test Anxiety on performance in Biology among secondary school students in North-west, Nigeria. The study employed correlational research design. The population of the study consists of all public secondary school two (SS2) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size of the study consists of 384 (Male, 213 And Female, 171) students selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The study adapted Self - efficacy Scale (SES) and Test Anxiety Scale (TAS) at 0.70, and 0.77 reliability co-efficient respectively. The statistics used for data analysis was the Pearson Product Moment Correlation and independent t-test. The findings of the study reveal no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west Nigeria. It is recommended that Schools should establish programs that will facilitate gains in self-efficacy as well as confident posture in approaching examinations, so as to promote Students' Academic performance in Biology.

Keywords: Adolescent, Gender, self-efficacy, test anxiety, academic performance

Introduction

Education is one of the vital sectors that contribute towards the development of any society. It is the backbone of every nation. In a situation were by majority of the people living in a particular society are educated, they would be able to come up with many ideas in terms of their economic, political and social wellbeing. However, education is also the light that can guide human beings in carrying out their day-to-day activities. Therefore, teaching and learning in Nigeria have to be considered as a Centre of gravity in educational context. If the students received a better and qualitative education, they would become well known important personnel in future who will lead to the development of the country.

Self-efficacy involves an individual's evaluation of own ability to achieve a goal or self-belief to do a specific task. For example, in academic situation, it can be assumed that learners with high self-efficacy would have higher motivation to learn, resulting in higher academic achievement, because those learners believe that they have an ability to achieve their goal. Self-efficacy refers to the confidence in one's ability to behave in such a way or to produce a desirable outcome (Siddiqui, 2015). Self-efficacy makes a difference in how people feel, think and act. It pertains to optimistic belief about being able to cope with a variety of stressors. Self-efficacy is defined as self-evaluation of one's competence to successfully execute a course of action necessary to reach desired outcome, (Zimmerman, 2020).

Tests at all stages of education have been considered as an important and powerful tool for decision making and determining academic success or failure. Students are evaluated with respect to their performance, skills and abilities (Habibullah & Ashraf, 2013). Scholars and researchers believe that no society or nation can develop more than the level and standard of education available for her citizens (Okafor, et al, 2018). Currently, the Nigerian system of education makes use of certificates to indicate the level of knowledge acquisition. However, before certificates are awarded, students have to be assessed or examined in the field they have been trained. Thus, examination becomes a yardstick against which students'

competence and progress are formally measured and appraised in the Nigerian education sector (Ozuome, et-al, (2020). On the other hand, anxiety is defined as feeling of undesirable and unclear like when person predicts a dangerous situation. Extreme level of anxiety impedes individual's mental and physical health and also has a negative effect on their personal, social, familial, occupational, and educational performance (Zahrakar, 2018).

It is perhaps ironic that students Biology achievement is on the decline (Tailor, 2016). A large number of people in current world do not receive proper education. Approximately 260 million of school aged children in the world can't read and write including in north-west and north-east Nigeria (World Bank, 2017). Above statement is one of the reasons why students level of self-efficacy is gradually decline, and students develop poor attitude to Examination Situations resulting to poor academic performance.

Most Students in North west Nigeria are suffering from low sense of self-efficacy, this avoid students to deal with tasks involving a high degree of difficulty like Biology, considering themselves incapable of solving problems and quickly losing confidence in their own capabilities thus displaying the tendency to remain focused on the experience of failures and setbacks (Siddiqui, 2015).

Test anxiety can be very stressful for students who experience it, leading to negative psychological wellbeing and developing low self-efficacy among adolescent students (Ahmad, 2020). Addiction alters perceptions, cognition, mood, behavior, and general body processes (Balogun, 2016). This may cause automatic anxiety in a testing setting among adolescent students and subsequently resulting in poor academic performance and the development of negative school attitude (Nnachi, 2007).

Given the aforementioned, the conclusions of this study will help to establish how best to assist and provide additional recommendations to develop positive self-efficacy and employ necessary measures to maximize academic performance.

Objectives of the Study

1. Examine the relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.
2. Determine the relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.
3. Determine the difference between male and female students' self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School students in North-west.
4. Determine the difference between male and female students' test anxiety among Senior Secondary School students in North-west.

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design, the research design facilitated broader coverage of a wide geopolitical area under examination within a potentially constrained time frame. It is the best design to use when a researcher wants to investigate the relationship between variables and compare groups, such as male and female.

The population of the study consists of all public secondary school two (SS2) Biology students during the 2022/2023 academic session in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size of the study consists of 384 (Male, 213 And Female, 171) students selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

Instrumentation

For the purpose of this study, the researcher adapted two (2) instruments for data collection. These are: Self - Efficacy Scale (SES) by Albert Bandura (1977), and Test Anxiety Scale (TAS) Abbasi & Ghosh (2020). More also, Biology Performance test was used to determine the academic performance of students in North-west Nigeria.

The Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to assess the reliability of the instruments. Cronbach alpha reliability test was used to determine the reliability of the instruments. Thus, the reliability coefficient of pilot testing result for self-efficacy scale (SES) was 0.70, test anxiety Scale (TAS) was 0.77. Furthermore, Biology performance test was 0.83 respectively.

The data collected was analyzed based on the null hypotheses formulated for the study. Hypotheses 1 & 2 was analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC), in addition, hypotheses 3 & 4 was tested using t-test for independent sample. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis One: there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 1: PPMC Summary Table showing the relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance.

Variable	Correlation, Sig. & N.	Self-efficacy	Academic performance
Self-efficacy	Pearson Correlation	1	-.080
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.117
	N	384	384
Biology performance test	Pearson Correlation	-.080	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.117	
	N	384	384

Note: ** means significant at 0.05 alpha level of Significance

Table 1, reveals a negative correlation (r- value = -.080) which is not significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance (r = -.080, p >0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes is accepted. The high negative correlation means no any significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance of Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west Nigeria

Hypothesis Two: there is no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 2: PPMC Summary Table showing the relationship between test anxiety and academic performance.

Variable	Correlation, Sig. & N.	Test anxiety	Biology performance test
Test anxiety	Pearson Correlation	1	-.124*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.015
	N	384	384
Biology performance test	Pearson Correlation	-.124*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015	
	N	384	384

Note: * means significant at 0.05 alpha level of Significance

Table 2, reveals negative correlation (r-value of -.124*) which is significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance (r = -.124, p < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes no significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance of Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west Nigeria is rejected. The result further assert that a unit increase in test anxiety can lead to unit increase in students' academic performance.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 3: t-Test Summary Table Showing the Difference in the self-efficacy of Male and Female adolescent Secondary Schools students (N=384)

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-val.	Sig.
Self-efficacy	Male	214	45.4065	13.2915	382	-1.08	.280
	Female	170	46.3808	13.3808			

NS: Not Significant at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 2 reveals no significant difference between male and female students' level of self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west, Nigeria. ($t = -1.08$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, Self-efficacy has nothing to do with gender.

Hypothesis four: There is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-Test Summary Table Showing the Difference in the test anxiety of Male and Female adolescent Secondary Schools students (N=384)

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-val.	Sig. (2-tailed)
Test anxiety	Male	214	43.0935	17.8843	382	-.190	.849
	Female	170	43.4353	17.0435			

Table four (4) reveals no significant difference between male and female students' level of self-efficacy among Senior Secondary School adolescents in North-west, Nigeria. ($t = 1.574$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, Findings reveals no difference in substances abuse among gender.

Discussion of Findings

The identification of the independent variables (self-efficacy and test anxiety) as correlates of academic performance of adolescents' secondary school students in North-west Nigeria, has been the major concern of this discussion.

Findings in Hypothesis one reveals there is no significant relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria. The finding is in line with Akanbi et-al (2015), Investigated the impact of self-efficacy on academic performance in colleges of education in Kwara State., Eukay, (2010) examined self-efficacy and test anxiety as correlates of academic performance among undergraduate students of a university in Eastern Nigeria. Results showed low significant correlation between self-efficacy and academic performance.

Hypothesis two reveals negative correlation (r -value of $-.124^*$) which is significant at 0.05 alpha levels of significance ($r = -.124$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which assumes there is significant relationship between test anxiety and academic performance in Biology among Senior Secondary School students in North-west, Nigeria. This support the above findings, Dawood et-al (2016) in a study titled relationship between test anxiety and academic achievement among undergraduate nursing Students, result revealed statistically significant positive relationship between test anxiety scores and undergraduate nursing students' academic level ($r = -0.144$, $p = 0.01$) which explain that undergraduate nursing students in higher academic level experience and less test anxiety. Pearson's R revealed a negative none statistically significant relationship ($r = -0.090$, $p = 0.157$) between test anxiety scores and undergraduate nursing students Grade Point Average. In a similar study conducted by Chowdhury (2022) titled "A comparative study on examination anxiety among Student academic performance" it was revealed that Examination anxiety is quite a common phenomenon among students across the world. However, anxiety entails various psycho-physical fallouts which interfere in the normal healthy living of many students, which revealed positive correlation among the variables. Euckay, (2010) examined test anxiety as correlates of academic performance among undergraduate students of a university in Eastern Nigeria. Test anxiety proves to be a significant predictor of the variability in academic performance,

Hypothesis three reveals there is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria. The value computed was ($t = -1.08$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. Finding of this research agrees with Baji, (2020). In research titled Analysis of Gender Difference in Academic Self-Efficacy and Achievements among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria. The findings of the study found that there was no significant difference in academic self-efficacy between male and female students. However, the mean value of female students indicated a higher-level self-efficacy (Mean =78.36) over the male students (Mean =78.16). The study also revealed a significant difference in achievements of male and female students. The mean difference showed that the male students performed better in academic achievements if compared with their female counterparts (Mean =105.42 for males and Mean =100.58 for females).

Hypothesis Four reveals there is no significant relationships in self-efficacy between male and female Senior Secondary School Biology students in North-west, Nigeria. ($t = 1.8$; $df = 382$, $p > 0.05$). Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This implies that, the assertion apparently further justified by the investigation of Ahmad (2020), shows that there is a meaningful difference between males and females considering the rate of test anxiety. As it is shown in table 2 the mean of test

anxiety score for female students ($X=123.72$, $SD=35$) was higher than the mean of test anxiety score for male students ($x=113.27$, $SD=32.14$). Similarly, this finding supported the result on Test Anxiety as reviewed on gender by Kusmawaty et al (2020), the results of the analysis showed that the mean of test anxiety in facing exams on male subjects was 3.10, while the mean of test anxiety in facing exams on female subjects was 3.35. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant difference in test anxiety in facing exams in male and female subjects.

Conclusion

The findings of this study revealed that the level of students' need to reawakened students' self-efficacy and brought out modality to address issue of test anxiety. Low self-efficacy resulted to students considering themselves incapable of solving problems and quickly losing confidence in their own capabilities and striving to meet up with their potentiality. Findings showed that students in North-west Nigeria have low self-efficacy. On the other hands majority of students are prone to test anxiety, resulted to low self-esteem, Low participation, negative attitude to learning, and poor academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researcher recommended that:

1. Schools should establish programs that will facilitate gains in self-efficacy as well as confident posture in approaching examinations.
2. Educational Psychologist should consider the psychological elements that contribute to severe exam anxiety in secondary school students and intervene accordingly.
3. Teach students how to manage and cope with test anxiety during exams, and make them understand that some level of anxiety is necessary as a motivator before the exam. Furthermore, examinations, ongoing assessment exams, and assignments should be adequately prepared to reduce unnecessary stress on students, which is likely to cause anxiety.

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References

- Abbasi, N., & Ghosh, S. (2020). Construction and Standardization of Examination Anxiety Scale for Adolescent Students. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education* 2020, Vol. 7, No. 4, 522–534
- Ahmad M.H, (2020). Investigate the Relationship between Psychological Well-being, Self-efficacy and Positive. *International Journal of Higher Education*. Vol. 9, No. 4; 2020. Press 138 ISSN 1927-6044 E-ISSN 1927-6052.
- Akanbi M. I., Godwin, A., Anyio B.T., Muhammad M, & Ajiboye S.A. (2015) Impact of Substance Abuse on Academic Performance among Adolescent Students of Colleges of Education in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.6, No.28, 2015
- Baji, M. I, (2020). Analysis of Gender Difference in Academic Self-Efficacy and Achievements among Senior Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), 659-675.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Self-efficacy*. In V. S. Ramachaudran (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of human behaviour*. Vol.4. (pp. 71-81). New York: Academic Press. Bandura, A. (Ed.) (1995). *Self-efficacy in changing societies*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Bandura, A. (1997).
- Balogun, S. K. (2016). Chronic intake of separate and combined alcohol and nicotine on body Maintenance among albino rats” *Journal of Human Ecology*, 19, (1), 21 – 24
- Chowdhury C.R (2022), A Comparative Study on Examination Anxiety Among Students in Relation to Gender and School Locales. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* ISSN: 2349-3429 (Print) Volume 10, Issue 2, April- June, 2022 DIP: 18.01.151.20221002, DOI: 10.25215/1002.151 [https:// www. ijip. In](https://www.ijip.in) (www.creativecommons.org/licenses/by/2.0),
- Dawood, E., Hind A., Rufa M., Nadiyah A., & Brouj A., (2016). Relationship between Test Anxiety and Academic Achievement among Undergraduate Nursing Students, *Journal of Education and Practice*. ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.7, No.2, 2016

- Eukay O.U., (2010). Self-Efficacy and Test Anxiety as Correlates of Academic Performance. *Journal of Educational Research*, 1 (10), 477-48
- Habibullah, S., and Ashraf, J. (2013). Factors affecting academic performance of primary school children. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Research*, 52, 2.
- Kusmawaty A, Ogunlesi, A.O., & Akindele, M.O. (2020). Nigerian secondary school teachers: a pilot survey of views and knowledge about drug abuse. *East African Medical Journal*. 69 (3), 140–145. 38.
- Nnachi, R. O., (2007) Advanced psychology of learning and scientific enquiries, Enugu: J. J. Classic Publisher Ltd.
- Okafor, E.O., Obi, J.S. & Oguzie, A.E. (2018). Relationship between students' self-esteem and their academic achievement in Imo state. *HOFA: African Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(1), 24-32.
- Ozuome, C.C., Oguzie, A.E., Mokwelu, O.B. & Anyamene, A. (2020). Locus of control as a correlate of secondary school students' academic achievement in Imo state, Nigeria. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 4(2), 374-385.
- Siddiqui S. (2015). Impact of Self-Efficacy on Psychological Well-Being among Undergraduate Students Shamsul Siddiqui. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*. ISSN 2348-5396 (e) | ISSN: 2349-3429 (p) Volume 2,
- Tailor, I. T. (2016). A meta-analysis of gender difference in creativity. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Florida state university
- Zimmerman, B.J. (2020). *Attainment of self-regulation: A social cognitive perspective*. In M.boekaerts, P.R. Pintrich, & M. Zeidner (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation* (pp.13-39). San Deigo, CA: Academic Press. 34.
- Zahrakar, F. (2018). The prevalence and effects of test anxiety in school children. *Educational Psychology: An International Journal of Experimental Educational Psychology*, 21(1), 89-101.